

INDIA'S ENERGY SECURITY: BALANCING DEPENDENCY ON WEST ASIA WITH ITS DIVERSIFICATION POLICY

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Abstract:

Energy is a security issue because it is required by every state to overcome its fear of being energy-insecure to energy-secure for its overall development. Energy security includes more than just the conventional means of ensuring energy supply at a fair price; it also involves important energy security factors like - energy prices, energy markets, the role of transit nations, geopolitics of energy, significant political upheavals in nations that produce energy, the impact of fossil fuels on the climate, and finally conflict or war imposed by one state on another in the hope of ensuring its own energy security. India, with a population of 1.4 billion, faces rapidly growing energy demands driven by industrial, residential, and transport sectors. Despite efforts to expand domestic production, dependency on imported crude oil and natural gas remains high, with West Asia, especially Iraq, Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and Qatar, playing a pivotal role. Balancing fossil fuel dependence with renewable energy transition remains central to India's strategy, as it navigates geopolitical complexities to ensure stable, sustainable, and affordable energy supplies in the coming decades. This paper is an attempt to analyse the India's energy dependency on West Asia, the Impact of global politics on India and West Asia energy trade and finally, India's attempt to diversify its energy supply, etc.

Keyword: India, energy security, energy diversification, West Asia, renewable energy, etc.

Introduction

According to the World Energy Outlook (2025), India is the largest source of energy demand growth globally. Energy demand increases by over 15 EJ (Exajoule) by 2035 in the STEPS, which is nearly as much as the demand growth in China and all Southeast Asian countries combined.

India is the largest contributor to growth in oil demand in this period, the second-largest for electricity generation and coal demand growth, and the third-largest for natural gas demand growth. Energy demand in India is being propelled by increasing economic activity. Between 2010 and 2024, its GDP growth rate was second only to that of China among major countries and regions. Before analysing the Indian concept of energy security, it is significant to understand various concepts related to energy security that have covered almost every aspect of energy security in general. Various scholars have defined Energy security may meaning different things in different nations. According to Andrews-Speed (2003), a traditional definition, energy security focuses on the need for a reliable supply of energy at a reasonable price. However, Isbell (2007) claims that it is difficult to define energy security; thus, the author defined it in terms of 'energy insecurity' and connected it to a timeframe. According to Yergin (2006), states must abide by several globally recognised standards, including diversification of supply, resilience, recognising the reality of integration, and ultimately the importance of information. By some American politicians and authors, the terms 'energy security' and 'energy independence' have come to be used interchangeably. While the majority of energy security specialists vehemently opposed the idea as it entails nationalisation, protectionism, and even isolationism, as a result, this strategy ultimately results in inefficiency, increased costs, supply shortages, and trade conflicts. Tillerson (2007), dealing with an almost comprehensive idea of energy security, has differentiated the nature of security of each energy mix, especially for oil and gas. According to Monaghan (2005) and Grant (2008), oil is a fungible commodity, which means that global market circumstances, not the laws of any particular state, determine oil pricing. For gas, the likelihood of an interruption and its likely effects are higher than for oil. Ciuta (2009) has made an effort to provide a comprehensive response to the question about the relationship between energy and security. He has defined this relationship in three different ways, namely the logic of war, the logic of subsistence, and the logic of totality. According to Baumann (2008), even though perfect security is never within reach, the concept of energy security gives rise to two unwarranted presumptions: first, that states with access to energy are 'secure,' while those without it are 'insecure.' Grant (2008) insisted that Governments that require energy frequently have to compromise other security, economic, political, and environmental

interests to obtain energy supplies. Cohen (2008) and Mansor (2008) have focused on various problems that are creating obstacles for the smooth functioning of energy security for nations, like increasing share in energy resources by developing countries, poor energy infrastructure, resource nationalism, food crops affected by the development of alternative energy sources and climate change, etc. Moreover, for Pritchard (2004) and Joffé (2007), the security of oil and natural gas pipelines from terrorist attack is a major challenge. García and Corrons (2003) have emphasised on problems dealing with radioactive waste and accidents in nuclear plants, etc.

The Concept of India's Energy Security

India's energy security explicitly came in 2008 under the title 'The Integrated Energy Policy' (IEP, 2008), this is the first comprehensive energy policy by the Indian government, which covers all sources of energy and addresses all aspects of energy use and supply, including energy security, access and availability, affordability and pricing, as well as efficiency and environmental concerns. Previously, the emphasis was on electricity shortage and unsatisfied energy needs. TERI (2015), in its report, mentioned that under the 12th Five-Year Plan, there was apprehension about energy security in the following manner: '*Energy security is obviously more difficult to ensure if there is a large dependence on imported energy*'. However, increasing dependence on imported energy sources, mainly oil, and gradually on natural gas and coal, resulted in greater government attention to the subject. As mentioned by IEA (2012), the three major policy objectives that India pursues in its energy policy are energy access, energy security and mitigation of climate change. All three objectives are closely related, but sometimes conflict with one another is derived from the reality in India. Thus, it is challenging for India to maintain a balanced approach in pursuit of all three objectives. Another important theme frequently occurring in the energy security concept of India is 'Self-sufficiency' or 'energy independence'. Although India adopted strategies of supply or fuel diversification to enhance energy security, it has placed a stronger emphasis on maximum utilisation of domestic resources, including hydrocarbon, thorium and renewables. In 2007, former Indian President APJ Abdul Kalam announced an ambitious plan to realise energy independence based on hydro, nuclear and renewable energy, stating,

‘we need to graduate from (talking about) energy security to (attaining) energy independence’. According to the Energy Security Index for India (2016), energy security is defined by the reliable provision of energy access to all citizens in a way that is both economically viable and environmentally sustainable. Based on this definition, India's energy security rests upon four core pillars:

- **Supply Reliability and Risk Reduction:** Ensuring an ample and consistent energy supply while actively minimizing associated supply risks.
- **Economic Viability (Cost-Effectiveness):** Providing energy at a cost-effective price point that is financially sustainable for all involved parties: consumers, suppliers, and the government.
- **Universal Access (Affordability):** Delivering affordable, modern energy solutions to every citizen.
- **Environmental Sustainability:** Maintaining a sustainable energy mix and effectively controlling emission levels over the long term.

The Government of India has also expressed its concern about clean energy and the environment at the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) held in Glasgow, United Kingdom, through *Panchamrit* (nectar elements):

- Reach 500GW non-fossil energy capacity by 2030.
- 50 per cent of its energy requirements from renewable energy by 2030.
- Reduction of total projected carbon emissions by one billion tonnes from now to 2030.
- Reduction of the carbon intensity of the economy by 45 per cent by 2030, over 2005 levels.
- Achieving the target of net zero emissions by 2070. (Ministry of Environment, 2022)

The Government of India (2024) has executed its ambitious project to achieve a developed nation status by 2047 under its ‘Viksit Bharat 2047’ initiative. It is committed to providing clean, reliable and affordable energy to all its citizens. The scenarios aim to identify pathways for

achieving national goals, such as energy security by 2047 and net-zero emissions by 2070. To achieve the target of Viksit Bharat 2047, various tools developed by NITI Aayog explore a wide range of potential energy futures by varying assumptions about economic growth, population, urbanisation, and technological adoption. It balances energy demand from sectors like transport, industry, and buildings with the projected supply from various sources. The latest version of the tool accounts for recent developments like the Green Hydrogen Mission, carbon capture-storage, and the growth of energy storage alternatives and finally a significant decline in import dependency, through increased use of renewables (NITI Aayog, 2023).

India's Energy Dependency on West Asia

India's energy mix is diverse, with a heavy reliance on fossil fuels, particularly coal, alongside growing contributions from renewables. While India has significant reserves of coal, it is relatively poor in oil and gas resources. India's total energy consumption in 2025 is estimated to be around 1800 (mtoe). India's total energy consumption was approximately 6.59 % of the world's total consumption (World Energy Outlook, 2025). A comparative study of India's primary energy consumption shows an increase across all energy resources between 2018 and 2025. The following data details the percentage share of each source in the total energy mix for both years.

Table 1: India's primary energy consumption in 2018 and 2025

Energy Source	2018 Share (%)	2025 Estimate Share (%)
Coal	45.88 %	48.00 %
Crude Oil	29.55 %	28.00 %
Natural Gas	6.17 %	8.00 %
Hydroelectricity	3.91 %	4.09 %
Renewable Energy	3.40 %	12.00 %
Nuclear Energy	1.09 %	4.00 %

Source: Lok Sabha (2025). Share of India in Global energy consumption. [https:// sansad.in](https://sansad.in).

India's Energy Import Dependency has also increased in crude oil and natural gas because energy production of India is not sufficient to meet the demand needs. As 40.9% of primary energy was imported in 2021-22, including 82.8% of crude oil and 45.3% of natural gas. India is the world's third-largest crude oil importer, with an import dependence of 88.2% in 2024-25. Import dependency for natural gas has significantly increased, jumping from over 30% in 2012-13 to around 48% in 2023.

Source: Raj, Yash. (2025). Iran-Israel conflict: Why is Iran crucial for the oil market? From where does India purchase oil? <https://www.bhaskarenglish.in/>

In 2025, India imported 40% of crude oil from Russia; its share increased after 2022 due to sanctions imposed on Russia by Western countries to demonstrate solidarity with Ukraine, making India a key

buyer of discounted Russian crude. In 2022, India imported 60% of crude oil from West Asia; however, this decreased to 44% in 2023. Imports from the Middle East declined by 28% in 2023 amid diversification efforts. In 2025, India imported 47.3% of crude oil from West Asia, especially from Iraq, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Kuwait, Qatar, etc. As the world's fourth-largest importer of LNG, India relies on foreign sources to meet 50% of its total natural gas demand. The majority of these imports come from West Asia, led by Qatar (48.6%) and the UAE (18.5%), with the USA also contributing significantly at 11%. As the IEA (2025) predicted, India is the new epicentre of growth in oil demand. Natural gas demand is expected to nearly double by 2035, reaching 140 bcm. Most of this increased demand will be satisfied through rising LNG imports. India's electricity demand is forecast to climb sharply, with sustained growth of over 4% annually. India's dependency on coal imports has steadily declined. It decreased from 26% in 2014-15 to about 21% in 2023-24. Furthermore, dependency has dropped to 19.60% in the fiscal year 2024-25 (up to January 2025). In essence, major reforms have resulted in record domestic production and a significant reduction in import reliance, reinforcing the coal sector's ability to meet India's growing energy

Oil Dependency

West Asia is a subregion of Asia that is bordered by Europe to the West, Central Asia to the North, South Asia to the East, and Africa and the Arabian Sea to the South. The region of West Asia roughly includes Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bahrain, Cyprus, Georgia, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Iran, Oman, Palestine, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Turkey, the United Arab Emirates, and Yemen. The main suppliers of oil to India are Iraq, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE. Russia has recently emerged as an important source. The key exporters of natural gas (LNG) are Qatar, the UAE, Saudi Arabia, and Kuwait. Qatar was the largest supplier to India in 2023 (<https://cms.kspp.edu.in>).

Table 2: India's Crude Oil Imports from the Gulf (in US\$ million)

<i>Sl. No.</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>2017-18</i>	<i>2018-19</i>	<i>2019-20</i>	<i>2020-21</i>	<i>2021-22</i>	<i>2022-23</i>
1.	Iraq	17,544.24	22,265.04	22,764.55	12,873.45	26,380.58	33,599.57
2.	Saudi Arabia	15,262.60	21,381.04	20,355.22	10,753.16	19,706.37	29,077.41
3.	Iran	8,978.76	12,110.72	994.81	Nil	Nil	Nil
4.	UAE	6,122.20	9,512.48	10,927.52	7,360.73	10,700.71	16,840.67
5.	Kuwait	5,283.96	5,430.90	4,840.35	3,126.93	6,551.90	8,024.61
6.	Oman	2,413.73	805.61	1,010.43	1,156.36	3,096.58	2,657.57
7.	Qatar	1,264.98	1,215.74	1,365.52	955.73	935.69	1,874.62

Source: Pradhan, Prasanta Kumar. (2004). India and the GCC States: A Growing Engagement. <https://www.researchgate.net/p-28>.

Energy is a crucial component of the relationship between India and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) nations (along with Iran and Iraq). India is heavily dependent on West Asia for its energy supply, a dependency that continues to grow due to India's increasing population, industrialisation, economic expansion and geographical proximity and resulting in lower transportation costs. (Pradhan, 2024: 28). The data available in the above Table -2 primarily illustrates India's heavy reliance on West Asian countries for its crude oil supply, with Iraq and Saudi Arabia being the pillars of its import energy supply. Iraq consistently remains the largest supplier of crude oil to India throughout the entire period shown. Imports from Iraq peaked at \$33,599.57 million in 2022-23. Saudi Arabia is the second-largest supplier in most years, with imports reaching \$29,077.41 million in 2022-23. The UAE is the third-largest supplier, particularly in the later years, with imports reaching \$16,840.67 million in 2022-23. It also clearly shows the economic shock of the 2020-21 pandemic and the major geopolitical shift that led to the termination of crude oil imports from Iran in the latter half of the period.

Natural Gas Dependency

The Gulf region is vital for India's energy security, supplying not only crude oil but also a significant portion of its natural gas (LNG) imports. Qatar is a crucial supplier, providing about half of India's total LNG imports (44% in 2021-22, valued at US\$5.9 billion). The UAE and Oman are also significant LNG suppliers (Pradhan, 2024: 28).

Source: Half of India's LNG imports come from Qatar and UAE, relying on Strait of Hormuz for supplies, June 2025, <https://www.shippingtribune.com/>

India meets half of its total natural gas needs through imports, which are highly vulnerable to disruption due to their dependence on the Strait of Hormuz shipping route. Over 50% of India's LNG imports are supplied by Qatar and the UAE, shipped through this strait. According to analysts, a prolonged disruption would cause supply delays, increase reliance on costly spot markets, and drive LNG prices up, negatively impacting the portfolio economics of India. Qatar's emergence as a major LNG supplier and its increasing role as a regional mediator have elevated its status as an essential partner for India. Qatar also views India as a key global partner for trade and investment. This role was reinforced by the

long-term deal signed in February 2024 between Petronet LNG and Qatar Energy for the supply of 7.5 million tonnes of LNG per annum from 2028 until 2048. Qatar's reliability is crucial for meeting India's growing energy demands, driven by urbanisation and industrialisation. Given the complex and volatile regional politics, Qatar offers India a perfect strategic partner due to its neutral mediator status and strong diplomatic ties across the region, including direct access to the Iranian leadership (Agarwal, 2025:1).

India's policy towards West Asia has undergone a significant transformation since 2014. The policy shifted from the 'Look West' initiative announced in 2005 (which had slow progress) to Prime Minister Modi's 'Think West'. It aims to deepen engagement in economic, defence, security, and strategic cooperation to safeguard national interests and promote regional peace and stability. India has amplified bilateral trade, revived efforts to sign a Free Trade Agreement (FTA) with the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), and established strategic partnerships. Indian public sector entities are actively participating in exploration, production, and pipeline projects in the UAE, Oman, and Iraq. There is a growing convergence of interests in green and renewable energy. India and key players like the UAE and Saudi Arabia have started collaboration in areas such as: Green Hydrogen, Electrical Interconnections, Energy storage technologies, Smart Grids and renewable energy investment. (Chinoy, 2024:1-3)

Cooperation in Renewable Energy

According to Pradhan (2024), both India and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries are committed to reducing their use of fossil fuels and increasing the share of renewable energy. India targets Net Zero Emissions by 2070, aims for 500 GW of renewable energy capacity by 2030, and intends to generate half of its electricity from renewable sources by 2030. The UAE is a strong partner, cooperating on green hydrogen. An MoU was signed in January 2023 for the development and investment in green hydrogen. I2U2 Project: As part of the I2U2 grouping (India, Israel, the UAE, US), the UAE is a key knowledge and investment partner in establishing a hybrid renewable energy project (wind, solar, battery storage) in Gujarat, India. India (with France) co-founded the International Solar Alliance (ISA) to promote solar energy. Bahrain, Oman, Saudi

Arabia, and the UAE have joined, recognising the benefit of investing their surplus wealth and abundant sunlight in solar technology.

Reasons Behind India-West Asia Energy Security Disruptions

India's imports are often affected by the regional instability of the Middle East, events like the Arab Spring and the Yemen conflict and every oil shock in West Asia has had an inevitable adverse impact on the Indian economy. During the 1973 oil crisis, India's energy import price rose by over 50 per cent. The direct overall adverse impact of the 1990-91 crisis on India's balance of payment was estimated at Rs 5,180 crore. In March-April 2003, the National Democratic Alliance (NDA) government had to impose an unpopular 15 per cent hike in fuel prices. Soon after taking over, the Congress-led United Progressive Alliance (UPA) had to raise the prices of petrol, diesel and liquefied petroleum gas. Kerosene was the only item left untouched to cushion the poor (Dietl, 2004: 382-383). The 2019 US decision to remove India from its sanction waiver list for purchasing Iranian oil forced India to stop transactions in US dollars and seek alternative, often costlier currencies. According to Raj (2025), West Asia has been a long-standing epicentre of geopolitical instability, with conflicts such as the Israel-Hamas war threatening regional security. These prolonged conflicts pose significant risks to its energy security, trade disruptions, rising oil prices, and potential threats to energy infrastructure are critical concerns for India's growing energy demands. The Israel-Hamas war, which erupted in October 2023, has now extended to Lebanon, Syria and is indirectly impacting Jordan and Iran. Key regional players like Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Kuwait, and Qatar have thus far remained uninvolved in the conflict. The overarching Israel-Hamas war and related proxy conflicts involving groups like Hezbollah contribute to a volatile environment, heightening the risk of sudden, unpredictable disruptions across the entire West Asian supply chain. The recent escalation of two regional conflicts, one involving Israel and Hamas and the other involving US actions against Iran, has severely worsened the situation in West Asia. Crucially, these conflicts have disturbed two vital energy transit routes: the Strait of Hormuz and the Bab el-Mandeb Strait. These two straits are extremely important for India's energy security as they are key passage points for the global energy supply.

Strait of Hormuz: The Strait of Hormuz lies between Iran to the North and Oman and the United Arab Emirates (UAE) to the South, linking the

Gulf to the Arabian Sea. It is just 33 km at its narrowest point, while the width of the shipping lane is only 3 km. This narrow waterway is one of the world's most critical maritime passages, with around 20% of global oil trade passing through it. 'Analysts and trade experts warn that Israel's assault on Iran and the rising tensions in the region present serious risks for India, including reduced oil supplies and a potential 40–50% surge in export costs'(www. www.business-standard.com).

Source: <https://www.shankariasparliament.com/current-affairs/strait-of-hormuz>, 2025

Around one-fifth of global liquid petroleum fuel consumption and global liquefied natural gas (LNG) trade transits the strait. Around one-fifth of the global liquefied natural gas trade also transited the Strait of Hormuz in 2024, primarily from Qatar. Given its geographic location, there is no sea route alternative to the Strait of Hormuz (www.broekmanlogistics.com). The Strait of Hormuz, a vital artery for global energy security, manages two-thirds of India's oil and half its liquefied natural gas supplies. Recent confrontations between Israel and Iran threaten to disrupt this crucial chokepoint, with potential severe repercussions for India's energy supplies, driving inflation and forcing sustained high interest rates. In retaliation, Iran may close the critical oil corridor Strait of Hormuz (SoH), which remains the only marine entryway into the Persian Gulf, with Iran on one side and Oman and the UAE on the other.

Sultana, Nasrin (2025). West Asia crisis: Is India insulated? <https://www.forbesindia.com/>

The given image provides a comprehensive view of the Significant Share of Global Oil Trade that transits through the Strait of Hormuz, detailing both the origin (exports) and the destination (imports) of the crude oil. In 2024, Saudi Arabia is the single largest contributor, accounting for 39% of the crude exports, while Iraq is the second largest, with 23%, the UAE contributes 15%, Iran, Kuwait and Qatar each contributed significantly. A combined 89% of the crude oil passing through the SoH originates from just three countries: Saudi Arabia, Iraq, and the UAE, highlighting the geopolitical importance of these relationships for global energy supply. The picture also shows that Asian economies (China, Japan & Korea, Rest of Asia, and India) collectively account for a massive 84% of the crude oil imports transiting the Strait of Hormuz, underscoring the critical nature of this strait for the economic stability of the entire continent. The Strait of Hormuz is very important for Indian energy security, as India imports 14% of the crude passing through this route. Much of India's oil from key West Asian suppliers like Iraq, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE reaches Indian ports via the Strait of Hormuz. A bulk of India's LNG imports, which come predominantly from Qatar, also come through this vital choke point. India is the world's third-largest consumer of crude oil and depends on imports to meet over 85 per cent of its requirement. Nearly 47 % of

crude oil imported by Indian refiners was likely to have been transported via the Strait of Hormuz. Closure of the Hormuz route will affect energy transport from these regions. The oil price rise also has a bearing on the country's trade deficit, foreign exchange reserves, the rupee's exchange rate, and inflation rate, among others. Iran itself depends on the Strait of Hormuz for its trade, particularly oil exports to China any blockade could impact Tehran considerably (Sultana, 2025).

The Red Sea route and the Bab El-Mandeb Strait: an attack on Israel on October 7, 2023, has brought cargo movement through Red Sea routes to a halt due to attacks by Houthi rebels on commercial shipping. Last year, the situation around the Bab-el-Mandeb Strait, a crucial shipping route connecting the Red Sea and the Mediterranean Sea to the Indian Ocean, escalated due to attacks by Yemen-based Houthi militants. Around 80 per cent of India's merchandise trade with Europe passes through the Red Sea, and substantial trade with the US also takes this route (Sultana, 2025). The Red Sea Strait is vital for 30 per cent of global container traffic and 12 per cent of world trade. Based on the tariff war impact, the World Trade Organisation (WTO) has already said that global trade will contract 0.2 per cent in 2025, as against the earlier projection of 2.7 per cent expansion. India's overall exports had grown 6 per cent on year to USD 825 billion in 2024-25. In 2025, it is expected to cross USD 900 billion. Snapping the two-month rising trend, India's exports declined by 2.17 per cent year-on-year to USD 38.73 billion in May due to a fall in petroleum goods' shipments (www.maritimegateway.com).

Source: Stanly, Johny. (2023). Bab El-Mandeb: A strategic choke point. www.thehindu.com.

Yemen-based Houthi rebels have targeted commercial shipping in the Red Sea and the Bab-el-Mandeb Strait in response to the Israel-Hamas conflict. This has forced many shipping companies, including those transporting oil and Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) to India, to reroute vessels around the Cape of Good Hope in South Africa, adding 10-14 days to journey times and increasing freight and insurance costs significantly (Stanly, 2023). Concerns regarding the possibility of a larger regional confrontation have been heightened by the increasing tensions between Israel and Iran. 'India has asked both parties to maintain caution and use communication and diplomacy to settle the problem because of its strategic interests in the West Asian area' (Nagendiran and Sathya, 2024:1) Indian energy security is also facing difficulties as a result of China's growing influence in West Asia, especially through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and China's closer connections to Saudi Arabia and Iran. India's strategic interests are threatened by China's expanding influence in the area, as demonstrated by its role in mediating the rapprochement between Saudi Arabia and Iran in March 2023 (Nagendiran and Sathya, 2024).

The key challenges to India's internal energy security, which need urgent resolution to establish a functioning energy market, are:

Energy Prices: State-owned companies (like ONGC, CIL) sell energy below international prices to keep consumer costs low, sacrificing profits and limiting necessary long-term investment. Policy makers must allow independent regulators to supervise and adjust prices to reflect actual costs. Public perception must shift to view energy as a commodity, not an entitlement, requiring sufficient resources. The petroleum and gas sector lacks an independent regulator, leading to rigid, government-set prices.

Energy Related Investment: While private investment has risen since liberalisation, major international companies remain hesitant to invest. Political infeasibility of gas pipelines from Central Asia/Middle East through Pakistan forces a costlier shift to imported LNG, requiring massive investment in LNG terminals.

Implementation of Energy Related Policies and Programmes: Slow and lengthy administrative processes are major barriers, stalling key energy projects. Better horizontal (inter-ministry) and vertical (Centre-State) coordination is crucial for effective project execution.

Transparency in Foreign Company Bidding: The dominance of large Indian, often state-owned, firms has worked against the full entry of foreign companies. Concerns about transparency have necessitated changes in the bidding process to ensure fair play.

Development of Renewables (RES): India's power generation remains heavily dependent on less efficient, more carbon-intensive coal. Implementation of clean energy policies is hampered by the centralised, state-owned sector and a lack of coordination, resulting in unclear and inconsistent policies between government levels. Around 90% of India's energy is met by fossil fuels (coal, oil, gas), leading to high carbon emissions, air pollution, and vulnerability to global price shocks. Renewable energy (RE) is often more expensive compared to existing fossil fuels. There is a lack of sufficient transmission and distribution infrastructure for RE, and the overall energy infrastructure, especially in rural areas, is often outdated and inefficient. (Anshu, 2025: 6-7). In addition to boosting energy supply to meet fast-growing demand, India is tackling a variety of other energy-related challenges. These include: ensuring universal access to modern energy; reducing fossil fuel import dependence; improving the reliability of electricity supplies; reducing air pollution; and cutting GHG emissions (World Energy Outlook, 2025:394).

The reliance of India on West Asia for energy faces multiple challenges that extend beyond regional geopolitical instability and domestic security concerns. The increasing energy consumption within West Asian nations themselves presents a significant complicating factor. The energy profile of West Asia is overwhelmingly dominated by fossil fuels, with natural gas (56%) and oil (41%) meeting nearly all the region's energy needs. This is notably higher than the global averages of 23% for natural gas and 30% for oil. The demand is intense; per capita energy consumption is more than double the average of other emerging market and developing economies (EMDEs). This escalating demand grew at an annual rate of 2.6% between 2010 and 2024, with natural gas demand alone projected to climb by 30% by 2035. Several factors drive this exceptional demands like- Electricity consumption is increasing even faster than overall energy demand, largely fueled by industrial consumption from the region's significant petrochemical sector, which is frequently integrated with refineries. Furthermore, high average incomes contribute to a high rate of car ownership (143 per 1,000 people, 45%

above the EMDE average), significantly boosting transport energy use. The extreme climate necessitates substantial energy for space cooling, as summer temperatures frequently exceed 40°C. Crucially, widespread water scarcity mandates the use of energy-intensive desalination processes. Commercial and residential buildings account for a substantial 64% of electricity consumption, with desalination alone consuming 4% of the region's electricity, largely relying on the approximately 80% of the world's thermal desalination plants situated in the region, which use oil and gas. Consequently, energy investment in the Middle East is exceptionally high, currently standing at 6% of GDP—double the global average. Projections for 2025 indicate a strong commitment to existing infrastructure, with approximately 78% of this investment anticipated to flow into fossil fuels, contrasting sharply with the global average of 35%. This combination of rapidly rising internal demand and sustained investment in fossil fuel infrastructure amplifies the challenges to India's energy security strategy concerning West Asia (World Energy Outlook, 2025:382 -385).

Measures to Mitigate Risks to India's Energy Security through Diversification

India's energy security is inextricably related to the stability of the Western Asian area. While the recent Israel-Hamas war presents substantial challenges, India can mitigate these risks by diversifying its energy sources and adopting a multifaceted approach through both domestic and external policy. According to Kumaraswamy (2020:103), the arrival of Prime Minister Narendra Modi marked a significant change in India's foreign policy, characterised by a 'summit-centric' approach. India is an energy-hungry nation, remaining heavily dependent on West Asia for oil and gas for the next 30-40 years. India consistently emphasises the status quo and non-interference (as seen in its stance on Iraq, Libya, and Syria) to protect its stability and economic interests. India tried to diversify its energy demand through internal and external policies.

Internal policies related to diversification: India currently faces major environmental and economic challenges due to its substantial reliance on fossil fuels. In 2023–24, India imported 232.5 million metric tonnes (MMT) of crude oil, resulting in a significant cost of ₹13,240 crore and contributing heavily to the country's 2.8 gigatonnes of Greenhouse Gas

(GHG) emissions. Reducing this dependency through biofuels, renewable energy adoption, and efficiency measures is essential for the country's sustainability and economic stability. India has made remarkable progress in diversifying and expanding its energy sector between the years 2014 and 2025, with a strong emphasis on renewable sources (Fathah, 2022:136-137). As per IRENA RE Statistics 2025, India ranks fourth globally in 'Total Renewable Energy Installed Capacity' and 'Wind Power', and third in Solar Power capacity. India's total installed power capacity reached 476 GW by June 2025 (up from 305 GW in 2015–16). This capacity is led by 240 GW of thermal, 110.9 GW of solar, and 51.3 GW of wind power. Solar capacity increased dramatically, rising more than 39 times from 2.82 GW in 2014 to 110.9 GW in 2025. The government has started various policies to promote and support Solar Energy, like: The National Solar Mission, PM-KUSUM Scheme, PM Surya Ghar Muft Bijli Yojana, etc. (Government of India, Energy Security in India, 2025:1-8). Wind capacity has secured the 4th position globally. Hydro capacity increased from 35.8 GW to 48 GW. Biopower capacity grew from 8.1 GW to 11.6 GW. Annual nuclear electricity generation saw a 60% increase, from 35,592 MUs (2014–15) to 56,681 MUs (2024–25). National Green Hydrogen Mission (NGHM) was launched in January 2023 with a ₹19,744 crore outlay. It aims to position India as a global leader in green hydrogen production, promoting energy self-reliance and reducing dependence on fossil fuel imports by ₹1 lakh crore by 2030 (India's Energy Landscape: Powering Growth with Sustainable Energy, 2025). Another important initiative taken by India is to expand and strengthen India's strategic petroleum reserves (SPR), which will ensure the country has a buffer during periods of global oil supply disruptions. For example, India's SPR, which currently holds 5.3 million tonnes of crude oil, can be expanded to protect the economy from short-term supply disruptions. Simultaneously, expanding India's own domestic energy production through investment in oil exploration and natural gas development will reduce reliance on imports. For instance, India's focus on offshore oil exploration in the Bay of Bengal can help bolster domestic energy production, reducing vulnerability to regional conflicts (Israel-Iran Conflict to Impact Oil Supply in India)

External policies related to diversification: West Asia is vital to India's energy security, supplying over 60% of its crude oil imports. In

2022-23, Iraq became the second-largest crude oil supplier to India after Russia. Political instability in the region often results in oil price volatility, which can significantly impact India's economy. To mitigate these risks, India is actively diversifying its energy sources, including agreements with Russia, the U.S., and Latin America (Chaturvedi, 2024:17). India's external energy security is based on foreign policy, energy diplomacy, and geopolitical conditions, focusing on source diversification. As with Myanmar, India is planning a pipeline to bring natural gas from the A-1 field to Bihar (GAIL and ONGC Videsh equity). With Central Asia, India joined the TAPI (Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India) pipeline project, which is politically easier due to ADB/Washington backing, and a regional power grid initiative. Indian and Chinese state firms (ONGC, Sinopec, CNPC) are increasingly cooperating in joint bids for overseas oil assets (e.g., in Syria, Sudan) and exploring broader cooperation in refining, trade, and exploration. ONGC Videsh (OVL) is actively acquiring global assets (e.g., Cuba, Brazil, Nigeria, Ivory Coast) to secure future supply. Also, a formal EU-India Energy Dialogue and Energy Panel were established to cooperate on clean coal, energy efficiency, clean energy promotion, and market reforms. They also launched an Initiative on Clean Development and Climate Change. India has established an oil relationship with Mozambique for India's long-term energy diversification and LNG supply security, potentially enhancing its access to affordable, long-term natural gas resources. India is also trying to keep access to Chabahar Port (Iran) as it is strategically vital for energy access, providing access to Afghanistan (bypassing Pakistan) and a potential road link to Russia (via Iran and Azerbaijan) for trade. On 21 November 2025, India and Afghanistan both agreed to support bilateral trade cooperation. That will help in fully operationalising the Chabahar Port route and launching regular shipping lines from Chabahar Port, developing of dry ports in Nimruz province and easing import-export processes (India, Afghanistan to appoint commercial attaches to boost bilateral trade, 2025). Moreover, strengthening diplomatic relations with oil-producing countries outside West Asia, like Africa and Latin America, can provide India with alternative energy suppliers. For example, India has increased energy cooperation with African nations like Nigeria and Angola, securing access to alternative crude oil sources. India is also trying to enhance maritime Security through cooperation with other nations can protect critical trade routes in the Persian Gulf and Strait of Hormuz (Raghavan, 2025). And finally, India's participation in international

bodies (IEA, IRENA, IAEA) and bilateral- multilateral agreements (India-US Strategic Energy Partnership) is crucial for harnessing new technologies, promoting sustainable energy, and contributing to global security.

Conclusion

India's energy security requires a constant balance between geopolitical reality and strategic ambition. West Asia remains, and will continue to be, a critical component of India's energy ecology, supplying the majority of its crude oil. The sheer volume and geographical proximity of Gulf hydrocarbons mean that India cannot and should not withdraw completely. Instead, the relationship has evolved into a comprehensive strategic partnership that prioritises reciprocal investments and long-term contracts over transactional dependency. However, diversification has become an existential necessity due to the unpredictability of the West Asian geopolitical landscape, which includes regional conflicts, international sanctions, and maritime chokepoint concerns like the Strait of Hormuz. India's energy cooperation with Russia and growing alliances with non-OPEC suppliers such as the United States and nations in Latin America and Africa. This geographic dispersion is important because it serves as a vital shock absorber against price spikes and regional crises. The only long-term route to genuine energy autonomy is provided by India's tremendous drive towards domestic renewables (solar, green hydrogen), increased domestic oil and gas output, and rising strategic reserves, even though fossil fuels will still predominate. A multifaceted approach is necessary to ensure India's energy security in the future, as the concept of energy Independence is not possible; however, India can reduce its energy dependency on West Asia through the development of a Renewable Energy Policy at the domestic level and exploring new avenues for energy sources.

References

- Agarwal, Rajeev (2025). From energy to diplomacy: Exploring the multifaceted India-Qatar relationship. www.economictimes.com.p- 1
- An Energy Security Index for India (2016). *Shakti Sustainable Energy Foundation*, New Delhi. <https://www.shaktifoundation.in>
- Andrews-Speed, Philip. (2003). Energy Security in East Asia: A European View. <http://www.dundee.ac.uk/al/>.

- Baumann, Florian. (2008). Energy Security as a Multidimensional Concept. *Policy Analysis*, (1). <https://www.cap.lmu.de/>
- Chaturvedi, Soumya (2024). Implication of Energy Transition on West Asian Stability. [https://indiafoundation.in/emailnewsletter-news-view-july-2024/images/pp 38-47](https://indiafoundation.in/emailnewsletter-news-view-july-2024/images/pp%2038-47).
- Chinoy, Sujan. (2024). India's West Asia Policy Under Modi in Chinoy, Sujan and Pradhan, Prasanta Kumar (ed.) (2024). *India's Policy Towards West Asia*, Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses, New Delhi, <https://www.researchgate.net/>
- Ciuta, Felix. (2009). From Oil Wars to Total Security: Conceptual / Contextual Notes on Energy Security. <https://www.allacademic.com>.
- Cohen, Ariel. (2008). The Real World: Global Energy Transformation. <https://www.arielcohen.com/index.php>.
- Conflict Escalation in West Asia Likely to Push Logistics Costs Up. 2024, https://www.business-standard.com/economy/news/conflict-escalation-in-west-asia-likely-to-push-logistics-cost-up-124100200590_1.html
- Dietl, Gulshan (2004), New Threats to Oil and Gas in West Asia: Issues in India's Energy Security Strategic Analysis, Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses, (28):3, pp-382-383.*
- Energy Security in India: Advancing Renewable Energy and Sustainability through Key Government Initiatives. (2025) Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, February, pp-1-8.
- Escalating Iran-Israel Conflict May Disrupt India's Trade with West Asia. 2025, <https://www.maritimegateway.com/escalating-iran-israel-conflict-may-disrupt-indias-trade-with-west-asia/>
- Fathah, M Abdul (2022). The Making of West Asia Forum: Security Factors and Areas of Cooperation. *Electronic Journal of Social and Strategic Studies* 3 (2) pp. 136- 137.<https://doi.org/1>
- García , Adolfo Calatrava and Corrons, Alejandro V. Lorca (2003). Energy: Geopolitics and Development. <https://www.iemed.org/anuari/2004/anarticles/acalatravalorca>.
- Government of India (2024). India Energy Scenario for The Year 2023-24. *Bureau of Energy Efficiency, Ministry of Power*. <https://beeindia.gov.in>.

- India's Energy Security: Balancing Dependency on West Asia – Anand
- Government of India, Press Information Bureau, <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressNoteDetails.aspx>
- Grant, Iain. (2008). Energy, Security, and Geopolitics: Could Someone Please Tell Us What We Mean ? https://www.cer.org.uk/pdf/briefing_eu_russia.
- IEA (2025). India Poised To Drive Global Oil Demand Surge. <https://www.energywatch.in/oil-and-gas/india-poised-to-drive-global-oil-demand-surge-says-iea>
- IEA. (2012). Understanding Energy Challenges in India: Policies, Players and Issues, <https://www.oecd.org>.
- India, Afghanistan to Appoint Commercial Attaches to Boost Bilateral Trade, 2025, <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com>.
- India's Energy Landscape: Powering Growth with Sustainable Energy, 2025
- International Energy Agency (IEA) (2007). World Energy Outlook 2007: China and India Insights. Paris/France: OECD/IEA. P- 444.
- Isbell, Paul. (2007). Revisiting Energy Security. <http://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/>
- Joffé, George. (2007). The Geopolitics of Energy Security. *Paper presented at the EUISS Annual Conference on Effective Multilateralism: Engaging with the new global players*, Paris. 1-6.
- Kalam, A.P.J.Abdul (2007). It's About Time India Gained Energy Independence. <http://www.financialexpress.com/news>
- Kumaraswamy, P. R. (2020). Great Powers Challenge India's Middle East Strategy, p-103 in Roy, Meena Singh, Quamar Md. Muddassir, ed. (2020) Changing Security Paradigm in West Asia: Regional and International Responses. KW Publishers Pvt Ltd. New Delhi.
- Lok Sabha. (2025). Share Of India In Global Energy Consumption. <https://sansad.in> .
- Mansor, Y.B. Dato' Shaziman Abu. (2008). Speech by Minister of Energy, Water and Telecommunications, Malaysia, Luncheon Address at the International Energy Security Forum. <https://www.energysecurityforum.com>.
- Middle East as a Source of Energy for India (2015-2025) https://cms.kspp.edu.in/public/issuebrief/issuebriefdocument_689db457341d2.pdf

- Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, India's Stand at COP-26, 2022, Delhi. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1795071>
- Monaghan, Andrew. (2005). Russian Oil and EU Energy Securit. *Conflict Studies Research Centre*, <https://www.defac.ac.uk/colleges/csrc/document-listings/russian/>.
- Nagendiran, K. and Sathya, R. (2024). Impact Of Israel-Iran- Iran War on the Indian Economy 9 (10). *International Journal of Novel Research and Development* (www.ijnrd.org)
- NITI Aayog (2023), India Energy Security Scenarios (IESS) 2047. Government of India. <https://www.iess2047.gov.in>
- OIL's Mozambique Area 1 LNG Project Moves From Hiatus To Restart Phase. 2024. <https://www.energywatch.in/oil-and-gas/oils-mozambique-area-1-lng-project-moves-from-hiatus-to-restart-phase>
- Pradhan, Prasanta Kumar. (2004). India and the GCC States: A Growing Engagement. In Chinoy, Sujan and Pradhan, Prasanta Kumar (ed.) (2024). *India's POLICY TOWARDS*
- Pritchard, Robert (2004). Promoting Investment to Enhance the Energy Security of Developing Countries. *Resources Law International*. <https://www.iea.org/textbasenpsum>.
- Raghavan T.C.A. Sharad, (2025). Israel-Iran Conflict To Impact Oil Supply To India, Increase Export Costs By 40-50%. <https://www.thehindu.com/business/israel-iran-conflict-to-impact-oil-supply-to-india-increase-export-costs-by-40-50/>
- Raj, Yash.(2025). Iran-Israel conflict: Why is Iran crucial for the oil market? From where does India purchase oil? <https://www.bhaskarenglish.in>.
- Sultana, Nasrin (2025). West Asia Crisis: Is India Insulated? <https://www.forbesindia.com/>
- TERI (2015). *Energy Security Outlook: Defining a secure and sustainable energy future for India*. New Delhi:: p-12- 14
- The Integrated Energy Policy (IEP, 2008). GOVERNMENT OF INDIA ATOMIC ENERGY LOK Sabha.(2011). <https://eparlib.sansad.in/bitstream/>
- Tillerson, Rex W. (2007). Changing Fortunes: Global Energy Security [http://www.ngoilgas.com/article/The High Seas of Trade: The Impact of Regional Conflicts on India's Economy. 2024](http://www.ngoilgas.com/article/The_High_Seas_of_Trade:_The_Impact_of_Regional_Conflicts_on_India's_Economy._2024)

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[https://www.broekmanlogistics.com/insight/the-impact-of-regional
conflicts-on-indias-](https://www.broekmanlogistics.com/insight/the-impact-of-regional-conflicts-on-indias-) -

WEST ASIA, Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses, New Delhi,
<https://www.researchgate.net/>

World Energy Outlook (2025). India's Energy Mix And Dependency
<https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2025.p-382-393>

Yadav, Anshu (2025). India's Energy Security Scenario: Challenges and
Opportunities. 7 (1): pp 6-7. www.ijfmr.com.

Yergin, Daniel. (2006). Ensuring Energy Security. *Foreign Affairs*, 85 (2) pp.
75-76.